

THE INTERFACIAL BONDING STRENGTH IN THE SQUEEZE CASTING PROCESS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Optimal manufacturing process in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system is investigated by measuring the interfacial bonding strength of single continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composite (MMC)s. Simple indentation method is uniquely adopted for its measurement of interfacial bonding strength. Obtained optimal manufacturing process with single continuous fiber reinforced MMCs is extensively applied for the fabrication of bundled SiC/Al and B/Al MMCs. The applicability of the process condition for actual MMC system is verified by measuring the interfacial bonding strength and the tensile strength of these bundled fiber reinforced MMCs.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composite (MMC)s are now considered not only for the structural material of hypersonic aircraft but also for the precision instrumental materials in missile guidance system and optical materials for the space applications 1. The candidate materials for the matrix are broadened to include titanium. However, the poor wettability between the reinforcing fiber and the matrix metal has narrowed the reliable manufacturing methods, which subsequently makes the manufacturing cost of MMCs high. In order to improve its wettability, there are several methods suggested such as coating of the fiber surface, adding surface active alloying elements to the matrix, applying an external pressure for the force impregnation, preheating of reinforcing the fibers, and superheating of the matrix 2.

It is uneasy to avoid of chemical reaction between the fibers and the matrix during the fabrication of MMC because of relatively high fabrication temperature of MMCs 3. In fact, chemically reacted interface causes weak interface which affects the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites significantly. Therefore, many attempts have been made to interconnect the interface condition, which is represented as the interfacial bonding strength, with the tensile strength of fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites 4-5. However, very little information is available on the bonding strength of MMC and on its measurement method. Furthermore, there is almost nothing available for the relation between the interfacial bonding strength and the manufacturing processes during the fabrication of MMCs. The aim of this study is, therefore, to bridge the interfacial bonding strength to the manufacturing process of a selected fabrication method of MMCs. Thus, the squeeze casting 6-7 is chosen to fabricate MMC in this study because this method includes some of above mentioned remedies to improve the wettability. For the measurement of the interfacial bonding strength of MMCs,

the indentation method is adopted due to its simplicity 8. Therefore, single continuous fiber reinforced MMCs are fabricated in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system under different manufacturing processes to do this research purpose. The influential manufacturing process parameters are consisted of the applied pressure, the temperatures of the superheating matrix and the preheating fibers, and the delay and the holding time of applying pressure. Each MMC specimen prepared under different manufacturing condition is measured its interfacial bonding strength by the adoption of indentation method with Vickers hardness tester. The effects of these influential parameters are summarized in a form of optimal manufacturing map on the basis of the results of single fiber reinforced MMCs 9. Obtained optimal manufacturing process map is evaluated of its actual applicability through using it for manufacturing bundled fiber reinforced MMCs.

SQUEEZE CASTING OF MMC

1. Fabrication of Single Fiber Reinforced MMC

Single continuous fiber reinforced MMC specimens are prepared in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system as shown in Fig.1 under different process conditions. The reinforcing single fiber is resolved from Avco's boron prepreg 5521-4 with acetone and the matrix is Al-13% Si alloy. The range of applied pressure is referred to the pressure drop in the inside of fibers caused by the meniscus curvature and the frictional force during the impregnation of the melt matrix 6 as a minimum pressure to overcome. The range of the temperatures for superheating the matrix and preheating a fiber is decided from the experimental results by sessile drop method to induce minimum contact angle between the fiber and the melt matrix.

2. Fabrication of Bundled Fiber Reinforced MMC

Bundled fiber reinforced MMC specimens are fabricated in the same squeeze casting system. Manufacturing process is taken from the results of optimal manufacturing process for single fiber reinforced MMCs. Fabricated bundled boron fiber reinforced MMC specimens are measured their interfacial bonding strengths and tensile strengths. The process conditions of SiC/Al MMC specimens are more refined from the observation of B/Al MMC results. Diameter of 15 μ m Nicalon SiC fibers are used for SiC/Al MMC specimens and these fibers are uniformly arranged in a specially designed preform holder.

MEASUREMENT OF INTERFACIAL BONDING STRENGTH

The interfacial bonding strength between the fibers and the matrix affects the mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites. For fibers which are well bonded to the matrix, the transfer of stress to the fiber appears to be understood in terms of the shear strength of the matrix and is not governed by the strength of the interface 10. However, MMCs which are usually fabricated under high temperatures have chemically reactive interfaces 3. Thus, the role of interfacial bonding strength is more critical in MMCs than in polymer matrix composites for the mechanical properties. The method of measuring the interfacial bonding strength is not well developed for MMCs. Available methods are divided into direct and indirect method depending on the shape of test specimen and back-up theory. However, these methods are mostly inappropriate for MMC because of the ductile behavior of matrix metal and difficulties of preparing specimen. Therefore, the indentation method which is recently applied for measuring frictional stress at the interface of ceramic ma-

trix composites 8 is uniquely applied for MMC here. The basic concept and the procedure of calculating the frictional stress at the interface is well explained in Ref.8. Therefore, if the hardness on the basis of the trace on the fiber is known from Vickers indenter, the interfacial bonding strength is easily calculated from the Eq.(1) and (2) of Ref.9.

RESULTS

The specimen size for the indentation test is decided as small as possible to avoid of having nonuniform stress distribution along the fiber direction. Thus, single continuous fiber reinforced MMC specimens which are made under different process conditions are cut into 5mm length and carried out the indentation test. The effect of the applied pressure on the interfacial bonding strength shows that the minimum applied pressure referred to Blake-Kozeny equation 6 is not enough to impregnate the melt matrix into the fibers. However, inappropriately high applied pressure brings the unexpected thing; breaking fibers. The effect of the applied pressure can not be separated from the effect of the temperatures of superheating the matrix and preheating the fibers. It is found that high superheating matrix temperature keeps the matrix liquid state so long to make the applying pressure in vain even though the pressure itself is appropriate. This draws to consider another parameter the delay time between pouring the melt matrix and applying pressure. In fact, this delay time decides the mushy zone state of the melt matrix during the solidification. These interconnected processing factors for the interfacial bonding strengths are summarized in one figure so called optimal manufacturing process map as shown in Fig.2. This map is believed to suggest some basic data to make sound MMC specimens in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system. Thus, this approach can reduce the leading time to develop the manufacturing process of new product.

Within the process conditions of hatched portion in Fig.2, bundled B/Al MMC specimens are prepared. As the fiber for single fiber reinforced MMCs is the same as this bundled fiber specimen, optimal conditions from the single fiber MMC do work in this bundled fiber MMC very closely as shown in Fig.3. This figure shows that 40 MPa applied pressure gives better interfacial bonding strength than 75 MPa, which was also happened during the fabrication of single fiber reinforced MMCs. Fig.4 shows the interfacial bonding strengths of bundled B/Al MMCs with respect to the preheating temperatures of the fibers. Some deviations are supposed to be occurred by incomplete uniform distribution of the fibers. The tensile strengths of these bundled B/Al MMC specimens are measured with respect to the fiber preheating temperatures parallel to the interfacial bonding strengths (Fig.5). Fig.4 and 5 combinely tell that the interfacial bonding strength is directly relative to the tensile strength, and both are affected significantly by the process parameters. Bundled SiC fiber MMC specimens fabricated by using the optimal manufacturing process are also investigated. This SiC fiber has smaller diameter than that of boron fiber. Therefore, the pressure drop between fibers is supposed to be higher than the larger diameter fiber for the same given area. Experiments verify it to show that higher applied pressure (75MPa) gives better interfaces than 40 MPa. Fig.6 shows the microstructure of SiC/Al MMC fabricated under 75 MPa. These MMC specimens are tested at different temperatures to observe the high temperature strength retention. Fig.7 shows that these squeeze casted SiC/Al MMC could retain their strength up to 350°C.

CONCLUSION

The effects of several manufacturing process parameters on the interfacial bonding strengths are investigated with single continuous fiber reinforced MMCs in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system. The simple indentation method is uniquely adopted for the measurement of interfacial bonding strength. As the process parameters are influenced by each other, optimal manufacturing process map is suggested to depict these interactive effects. By measuring the interfacial bonding strength and the tensile strength of bundled fiber reinforced MMCs, which are manufactured according to the optimal manufacturing process map. It is shown that the optimal manufacturing processes of single fiber reinforced MMC can be reliably extended to the fabrication of bundled fiber reinforced MMC. Also, it is found that squeeze casted SiC/Al fabricated under the optimal processing condition can retain its tensile strength up to 350°C without significant loss.

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Fig.1 Schematic Drawing of a Vacuum Assisted Squeeze Casting Machine

Fig.2 Optimal Manufacturing Process Map in a Vacuum Assisted Squeeze Casting System

Fig.3 Microstructure of B/Al-13%Si MMC

Fig.4 Bonding strength of B/Al-13%Si MMC with Respect to the Mold Temperature

Fig.5 Tensile Strength of B/Al-13%Si MMC with Respect to the Mold Temperature

75MPa, 800/500.10/35, Vac. (x400)

Fig.6 Microstructure of SiC/Al MMC

Fig.7 Tensile Strength of SiC/Al MMC with respect to the Test Temperature